

A Design Methodology for Compositional Simulation: The Digital-Twin Interconnect Framework

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Abstract - In this paper, we present the design methodology behind Veloce System Interconnect (VSI). An optimized interconnect framework enabling heterogeneous clients' connections to create digital twins of cyber-physical systems. The design methodology is based on three enabling pillars: the gateway concept, Digital Twin Description Language (DTD), and automation flow (VSIBuild, VSISim). An adaptive headlight application is used as a demonstration of the interconnect framework.

Keywords: *digital twins, cyber-physical systems, co-simulation, pre-silicon verification*

Introduction

OEMs are starting to own their chip design flow so extending the System on a Chip (SoC) design & verification landscape to digital twins & industrial metaverse is becoming a necessity. Digital Twins (DTs) of Cyber Physical System (CPS) involve both continuous and discrete modeling for its subsystems. The computing subsystems are modeled at different levels of abstraction, including system or formal level, pre-silicon, virtualized HW platforms or SoC designs on Hardware Accelerated Verification HAV platforms and post-silicon on external boards. Furthermore, cloud connectivity is a key element to tie the digital twin with its Physical Twin (PT) to close the gap between what was designed versus what was produced. Interactive digital twins can also involve humans (human-in-the-loop) with the latest virtual reality/augmented reality headsets and data driven immersive analytics features. Building digital twins with such diverse and different domains components needs the existence of a system interconnect framework enabling heterogeneous clients' connections and co-simulating all digital twin elements, in a synchronized and deterministic manner.

Product Solution

Veloce System Interconnect (VSI) [1] is an optimized interconnect framework enabling heterogeneous clients' connections as shown in Figure 1 to create digital twins in automotive, robotics, avionics, and medical verticals. The interconnect features conform with well-established electronic design automation standards: SystemC TLM 2.0, JModelica FMI 2.0, and Inter Process Communication (IPC) connections.

VSI allows connections of different client types e.g. sensor/scenario simulators, mechatronic systems simulators, dashboard software, cloud services, compute/think modules at different abstraction levels including C/C++ modules, and any platforms that have C/C++ interfaces, SystemC TLM models, python modules, ROS modules, Virtual SoC Platforms, Register Transfer Level (RTL) designs modelled using Hardware Description Languages (HDL) on digital simulators, Hardware Assisted Verification (HAV) platforms and external HW boards with physical connections (e.g. Ethernet, CAN).

Methodology

The design methodology behind VSI is based on three enabling pillars as shown in Figure 2: the gateway concept, Digital Twin Description Language (DTD) and automation flow for building the interconnect framework.

Figure 1: Product solution – Veloce System Interconnect

Figure 2: Methodology – Veloce System Interconnect

The Gateway Concept: Each digital twin component port is connected to VSI backplane server through a “gateway”. A gateway executes data conversion and routing into VSI simulated & physical communication protocols. Gateways are categorized: Language2Protocol (C++/C#/SystemC/Python/ROS), Pre-Silicon (VPs, RTL), Post-Silicon (HiL) and Specialized (Sensors, Actuators, Cloud Services, 3rd party Tools). Communication Protocols of the backplane server include for example: Ethernet, CAN, AXI, etc.

Digital Twin Description Language: This is an intermediate & proprietary language format upon which system modelling languages can be built on top. It defines the connectivity between different digital twin components. The syntax and semantics of this language is beyond the scope of this paper for space limitation, but the concept can be demonstrated with the example in Figure 3, where we connect a virtual platform with a mechanical system exported as a Functional Mock-up Unit (FMU). We start by defining two ports with proper gateway types. Configuring the port sockets (port number, port type), adding the MAC and IP addresses, defining the port signals, and configuring the data exchange between ports. This is the case for Ethernet protocol backplane.

The Automation Flow: mainly eases the generation of the infrastructure of the backplane server & remote clients' gateways needed to connect heterogeneous components including think, sense, actuate and connect elements.

VSIBuild (Digital Twin Builder): Developing user's own digital twin configuration requires a relatively high level of knowledge and expertise in many areas and considerable amount of development time. VSIBuild provides an automated flow where users can create the skeleton of their desired digital twin configuration easily from DTDL.

VSI Sim (Digital Twin Simulator): The simulator provides an interface to the user to be able to control the simulation time and display information about the digital twin during the simulation. An X-Term window pops up for each of the DT components and a command prompt interface for "VSI Simulation Control" that provides a full control over the time advancement and can display some useful information about the system.

```
add port -type Fmu -gateway fmu2DtEthernet -fmuPath <path_to>/DriveLineFmuExport.fmu -name drivelineFmu
add port -type VirtualPlatform -gateway vpEthernet2DtEthernet -vpPath <path_to>/RCar-M3_install -name rcarM3Vp

config port -portName drivelineFmu -protocol tcpIp -macAddress 12:34:56:78:9a:be -ipAddress 192.168.2.2
config port -portName rcarM3Vp -protocol tcpIp -macAddress 12:34:56:78:9a:bd -ipAddress 192.168.2.3

add portSocket -portName rcarM3Vp -ipPortNum 8080 -socketType server
add portSocket -portName drivelineFmu -ipPortNum 8080 -socketType client

define portSignals -portName drivelineFmu -signals [expseu .torque:double:input,expseu .rotary_speed:double:output]
define portSignals -portName rcarM3Vp -signals [axleSpeed:double:input,engineTorque:double:output]

connect signals rcarM3Vp.engineTorque drivelineFmu.expseu .torque
connect signals rcarM3Vp.axleSpeed drivelineFmu.expseu .rotary_speed
```

Figure 3: Digital twin description language

Results and discussions

An adaptive headlight is a SW defined feature in cars to adjust the lighting according to the steering angle. In this case study we highlight the refinement steps needed to go from the headlight controller fully implemented as SW (e.g. C/C++) running natively on PC to Virtual SoC Platform running on PC or on a Virtual Private Cloud (VPC) on cloud and finally as an SoC design running on HAV Platform (e.g. FPGA prototyping System) [2]. This is commonly referred to as refinement from Software-in-the-loop to Pre-Silicon (Processor)-in-the-loop.

Figure 4: Refinement from Software-In-the-Loop to Processor-In-the-Loop

The digital twin configuration in addition to the ECU model of the headlight controller includes the headlight sensor modelled in Simcenter Prescan scenario simulator [3] and a servo motor that controls the headlight modelled and exported as FMU using Simcenter Amesim mechatronics simulator [4]. Figure 5 shows setup of all three configurations using C++, VP, and RTL CAN Gateways. In this case, we used CAN protocol as backplane.

Figure 5: Digital Twin configurations of adaptive headlight use-case.

Figure 6: Adaptive Headlight System: virtual sensor to CAN gateway (left) simulation running in Simcenter Prescan (middle), and Analysis from VSISim simulation w/Sourcery Analyzer (right)

Conclusions and implications

Using VSI in the demonstrated use-case, we achieved the followings:

1. “Integrated toolchain” by demonstrating integration of Simcenter Amesim, System Level Apps (SystemC, C/C++ or ROS), Simcenter Prescan and pre-silicon hardware accelerated verification platforms.
2. “Model Refinement with intact digital twin components” by demonstrating the refinement of the controller under test while keeping other digital twin components intact within the loop. The success criterion is to obtain the same results, which demonstrates the effectiveness of the controller design synthesis.
3. “Automated Flow”, as it only takes minutes to automatically generate the infrastructure needed to connect different digital twin components, by using Digital Twin Description Language (DTDLD).

References

- [1] Siemens EDA Pave360 backplane. Available at: <https://resources.sw.siemens.com/en-US/fact-sheet-pave360-backplane>
- [2] ProFPGA Available at: [FPGA Prototyping | FPGA based Prototyping | FPGA Board Multi-FPGA \(profpga.com\)](https://www.profpga.com/)
- [3] Siemens Simcenter PreScan. Available at: <https://plm.sw.siemens.com/en-US/simcenter/autonomous-vehicle-solutions/prescan/>
- [4] Siemens Simcenter Amesim. Available at: <https://www.plm.automation.siemens.com/en/products/lms/imagine-lab/amesim/>.

Acknowledgments:

HORIZON JU Innovation Actions | 101139048| ENVELOPE - HORIZON-JU-SNS-2023

Co-funded by
the European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union's Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU) under grant agreement No. 101139048. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or SNS JU. Neither the European Union nor SNS JU can be held responsible for them.